

Poleward intrusion in the northern Galician shelf

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Abstract. The evolution of a warm water mass related to the Iberian Poleward Current (IPC) was characterized along the northern Galician shelf in November 2008 by means of Sea Surface Temperature and wind data. It was observed that under upwelling favorable conditions water temperature decreased along the northern coast and a temperature break appeared between Cape Vilano and Cape Ortegal showing a relaxation of the poleward intrusion. The effect of the IPC was also analyzed inside the northern Galician rias taking into account the hydrographical and biogeochemical properties measured on November 18. Water driven by the IPC was observed close to the mouth of the rias, around Cape Estaca de Bares, causing a nutrient salts decrease. Inside the rias a slight biological activity was found near surface resulting from fluvial contributions.

Keywords: Iberian Poleward Current; Northern Galician Rias; SST; Ekman transport; thermohaline variables; nutrient salts; chlorophyll.

1. Introduction

Several water masses have been identified around the northwestern continental margin of the Iberian Peninsula. From spring to summer, Eastern North Atlantic Central Water (ENACW) is present near the coast (Rios et al., 1992; Prego et al., 1999) while during late autumn and winter the Galician offshore seawaters are under the influence of a northward surface current, which flows over 1500 km along the Iberian margin (Frouin et al., 1990; Haynes and Barton, 1990). This current, known as the Iberian Poleward Current (IPC), is a layer of 25-40 km wide and about 200 m deep.

35 The spatial importance and variability of intrusions of ENACW along the Galician
36 shelf has been extensively studied (Wooster et al., 1976; Rios et al., 1992; Alvarez et al.,
37 2005) especially at the western Galician Rias Baixas and its neighboring sea area due to
38 the regular occurrence of upwelling events. The different orientations of the Galician
39 coastline influence upwelling frequency and intensity and as result, upwelling favorable
40 conditions are prevalent in spring-summer along the western Galician coast but not along
41 the northern one (Gomez-Gesteira et al., 2006; Alvarez et al., 2009). Therefore, upwelling
42 research has been mainly focused south of Cape Finisterre and it has been considered a
43 typical spring-summer process driving ENACW into the estuaries (Prego et al., 1999;
44 Alvarez et al., 2005). However, this phenomenon can also be observed in fall-winter under
45 northerly winds blowing at the shelf. These winter upwelling events can pump inside the
46 estuaries seawater associated with ENACW (deCastro et al., 2006; deCastro et al., 2008) or
47 driven by the IPC (Alvarez et al., 2003; Prego et al., 2007). Because of the occurrence and
48 intensity of the IPC varies between years (Pingree and LeCann, 1990; Garcia-Soto et al.,
49 2002) the intrusion of this water mass inside the estuaries is not a well studied
50 phenomenon. Thus, the influence of the IPC has been investigated mainly along the
51 Galician shelf in relation to plankton distribution (Fernandez et al., 1993; Huskin et al.,
52 2003; Cabal et al., 2008).

53 From Cape Finisterre to Cape Ortegal (Fig. 1) upwelling events associated with the
54 presence of ENACW have been also observed in summer at the Artabro Gulf (Prego and
55 Varela, 1998) although these events are less common than along the western Galician coast
56 and generally restricted to a band near the edge of the continental shelf (Prego and Bao,
57 1997; Varela et al., 2005). Eastward of Cape Ortegal there is not information about wind
58 induced events except a recent characterization of a winter (February 2008) upwelling
59 event which introduced shelf bottom seawater inside the northern Galician rias (Alvarez et
60 al., 2009).

61 The present study aims to contribute to the knowledge of the processes which affect the
62 northern Galician coast in terms of water masses and wind induced phenomena. On the one
63 hand, the presence of a warm water mass related to the IPC at the northern Galician shelf
64 in November 2008 will be characterized by means of Sea Surface Temperature and wind
65 data. On the other hand, the influence of this water mass on the chemical and biological
66 patterns will be analyzed inside the northern Galician rias.

67

68 **2. Material and methods**

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70 **2.1. Area under study**

71

72 The northern Galician Rias of Ortigueira (38 km² of surface), O Barqueiro (10 km²)
73 and Viveiro (27 km²) are located along the northern Galician coast (Fig. 1), eastward of
74 8°W (Cape Ortegal). They are dominated by marine processes except at the inner estuarine
75 (mesotidal) zone which is partially enclosed with well-developed beach barriers (see
76 Alvarez et al., 2009 for a complete description). At the innermost area, these rias receive
77 the fluvial discharges of the Mera (Ortigueira Ria), Sor (O Barqueiro Ria) and Landro
78 (Viveiro Ria) Rivers, whose annual average volume of water is 4.2, 6.0 and 7.1 m³·s⁻¹,
79 respectively. The annual average air temperature is 14°C with a thermal fluctuation of 10°C
80 and rainfall varies between 1100-1800 mm yr⁻¹. The wind regime is characterized by
81 westerly winds in autumn-winter, while in spring and summer easterly winds prevail.
82 Nevertheless, easterly winds can be also observed in autumn-winter (Gomez-Gesteira et
83 al., 2006; Alvarez et al., 2009).

84

85 **2.2. Atmospheric variables**

86

87 Surface wind fields during November 2008 were provided by the QuikSCAT satellite
88 (http://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/DATA_CATALOG/quikscatinfo.html). The data set consists of
89 global grid values of meridional and zonal components of wind measured twice daily on an
90 approximately 0.25×0.25° grid. An average between both measurements was considered.
91 Wind speed measurements range from 3 to 20 m s⁻¹ (accuracy: 2 m s⁻¹ and 20° in direction)
92 and the reference height of wind data is 10 m. In addition, wind data close to the coast (~25
93 km) are not available due to the existence of a small coast mask. However, previous
94 studies have shown that QuikSCAT data are comparable to modeled data in this area
95 (Gomez-Gesteira et al., 2006).

96 Ekman transport was calculated using wind data and was analyzed along the whole
97 Galician coast and at five control points considered along the northern coast at the latitude
98 44.25°N (black dots, Fig. 1(b)). The obtained discrete series covers from 8.25°W to
99 7.25°W. Data were averaged for the two previous days to each date under study. This
100 average was considered because of atmosphere-ocean interactions take place on a wide
101 range of spatial and temporal scales and the effect of the wind pushing on the ocean
102 surface has not an immediate response.

103 Sea Surface Temperature (SST) data were obtained from the National Centre for Ocean
104 Forecasting (NCOF) (<http://www.ncof.co.uk/>) by means of the Operational Sea Surface
105 Temperature and Sea Ice Analysis (OSTIA) system. OSTIA uses satellite data provided by
106 the GHRSSST project (<http://ghrsst.jpl.nasa.gov/>), together with in-situ observations to
107 determine the sea surface temperature for the global ocean with a resolution of
108 approximately 5 km. SST images were analyzed around the Galician coast. In addition,
109 five control points were considered in front of the northern Galician rias in a perpendicular
110 section at approximately 7.7°W (black squares, Fig. 1(b)).

111

112 **2.3. Hydrographical and hydrochemical measurements**

113

114 A cruise was carried out at the northern Galician rias onboard the R/V *Mitylus* in
115 November 18, 2008. Vertical profiles of salinity, temperature and chlorophyll-a were
116 measured with a CTD sounder Sea-Bird 25 in several stations placed inside Ortigueira,
117 Barqueiro and Viveiro Rias and their adjacent shelf (asterisks in Fig. 1(a)). Moreover, one
118 section with five stations located along the main channel of each ria was considered (St.3
119 to 7, black dots in Fig. 1(a)). The water column was sampled at 0, 5, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 m
120 depth using General Oceanic 10 L bottles by means of a General Oceanic Rosette.
121 Dissolved oxygen, nutrient salts and chlorophyll-a sub-samples were taken for analysis.

122 Daily river flows of the main rivers running into the three northern rias during
123 November 2008 were supplied by the ‘Aguas de Galicia’ company. Moreover, a telescopic
124 pole with a bottle holder was used to collect water samples in these three rivers at the
125 fluvial end-limit of estuaries in November 17, 2008. Salinity and temperature were
126 measured using WTW Multiline P4 sounder and dissolved oxygen, nutrient salts and
127 chlorophyll-a sub-samples were taken for analysis.

128 Daily air temperature was supplied by the Regional Weather Forecast Agency
129 (METEOGALICIA). Data were measured at the meteorological station located 43.66°N
130 and 7.56°W (black square in Fig. 1(a)).

131 Next day to sampling, dissolved oxygen was analysed in the water samples following
132 the Winkler method (Grasshoff et al., 1999) making use of a 702-MS Titrino (Metrohm).
133 Then oxygen saturation percentages were calculated from the dissolved oxygen
134 concentration, salinity and temperature data of the sample. Nutrient salts were analysed
135 (Grasshoff et al., 1999) in an Integral Futura (Alliance Instruments) autoanalyzer system
136 with separate lines to nitrate, nitrite, ammonium, phosphate and silicate determinations.

137 Chlorophyll-a concentration, after sample filtration through Whatman GF/F filters and
138 extraction with 90% acetone (Unesco, 1994), was determined by spectrofluorimetry. From
139 the chlorophyll-a result along the sections, CTD fluorometer was calibrated.

140

141 **3. Results and Discussion**

142

143 **3.1. Sea surface temperature conditions and Ekman transport patterns**

144

145 SST images were considered around the Galician coast during the previous days of the
146 cruise carried out on November 18 (color maps in Fig. 2) to analyze the intrusion process
147 of warm seawater at the northern Galician shelf and rias. SST image corresponding to
148 November 14 showed the presence of a warm superficial water mass near the Galician
149 coast with temperatures around 14.8-15.5°C in front of the northern Galician rias (Fig.
150 2(a)) and around 16°C near the continental slope of the western Galician shore. This water
151 mass can be associated with the IPC, which runs from the south of Portugal to the north of
152 the Bay of Biscay (Frouin et al., 1990; Haynes and Barton, 1990) and can be identified by
153 a signal warmer than the surrounding ones (Garcia-Soto et al., 2002) as shown in Fig. 2.
154 IPC presence was discontinuous along the Galician coast showing a break between Cape
155 Vilano and Cape Ortegal with temperature values around 14.5-15.0°C. On November 15
156 (Fig. 2(b)), this gap almost disappeared and temperature increased to 15.5-16.0°C. During
157 the next few days (Fig. 2(c-f)) the break was re-established and the gap between offshore
158 areas of the western and northern Galician rias appeared again with a temperature decrease
159 till 14-15°C.

160 The observed trend of the IPC evolution along the Galician coast may be explained in
161 terms of meteorological forcing considering Ekman transport patterns (arrows in Fig. 2). In
162 November 14 (Fig. 2(a)) transport was mainly directed southward piling surface waters up
163 onto coast and creating downwelling conditions along the northern Galician shelf. The next
164 day (Fig. 2(b)), negligible values of Ekman transport were measured along the northern
165 coast without any prevailing direction. This situation agreed with a temperature increase at
166 the area between Cape Vilano and Cape Ortegal showing an almost continuous
167 temperature signal along the Galician coast. From November 16 on (Fig. 2(c-f)),
168 northeasterly winds prevailed along the Galician coast (upwelling favorable conditions).
169 The above mentioned gap with lower temperature values between capes at the northern

170 shelf appeared again and a continuous SST decrease was observed at the Galician shelf
171 showing the weakening of the temperature signal.

172 Previous studies have indicated the importance of wind forcing in controlling the IPC
173 intrusion at the adjacent shelf. So, Gonzalez-Pola et al. (2005) found that downwelling
174 pulses can reinforce the observed IPC signal at the western Cantabrian coast. Therefore,
175 years of sustained and frequent downwelling events can be apparently related to intense
176 penetration of the IPC. On the contrary, during upwelling events the IPC might lose its
177 surface expression and become displaced offshore (Peliz et al., 2005) and the entrance in
178 the Cantabrian coast can even stop (Ruiz-Villareal et al., 2006). In a short time scale, e.g.
179 six days, this trend has been highlighted in the northern Galician shelf by means of the
180 meridional component of Ekman transport (Q_y) and SST data measured near the northern
181 Galician rias (Fig. 2(g)). A period of positive Q_y values (upwelling favorable) was
182 observed during the three days previous to the cruise under study (18 November) agreeing
183 with a decrease of surface water temperature that pointed out a relaxation of the poleward
184 intrusion.

185

186 **3.2. Influence of the IPC on the Northern Galician Rias**

187

188 The general view offered in the previous section about the poleward evolution along
189 the northern Galician region using satellite images and wind data, was also analyzed *in situ*
190 by means of an oceanographic cruise carried out inside the rias. Surface isotherms (1m
191 deep) from CTD data (Fig. 3(a)) indicated an offshore temperature gradient ranging from
192 13.7°C at the innermost zone of Ortigueira Ria to 15.4°C at the adjacent shelf around Cape
193 Estaca de Bares. Close to this cape the surface thermocline was observed: 1°C (14.2-
194 15.2°C) in 1.4km of distance. According to the previous discussion on SST maps, the
195 observed surface temperature distribution was established by the IPC influence.

196 A three-dimensional draw of the intrusion was provided by means of TS diagrams of
197 the water column corresponding to inshore and offshore areas of the Northern Galician
198 Rias (Fig. 3(b)). A quasi-linear mixing was observed at the mouth of the three rias (Om,
199 Bm and Vm, Fig. 1(a)) resulting from the fluvial influence, highlighted by the high flow of
200 Sor River (Table I) in the case of Bm station. Taking into account that at the northern
201 Galician region upwelling favorable conditions were established four days before
202 November 19 (Fig. 2), thermohaline variables at these stations could indicate the presence
203 of upwelled water. Nevertheless, TS profiles showed that this water cannot be associated

204 with ENACW or IPC. Previous studies indicated that at the western Galician coast
205 upwelled water (ENACW or IPC) can be identified inside the estuaries when favorable
206 conditions persist at least that number of days (Alvarez-Salgado et al., 2000; Alvarez et al.,
207 2005). At the northern Galician coast, Alvarez et al. (2009) pointed out an upwelling event
208 after nine days of favorable winds although upwelled water corresponded to shelf bottom
209 water which was not associated with ENACW or IPC.

210 Off Viveiro and O Barqueiro Rias (st. E and F, Fig. 1(a)) the presence of a warm and
211 saline water mass with values around 15°C and 35.60-35.65 was observed in the upper
212 layers of the water column. These conditions were also observed around Cape Estaca de
213 Bares (st. C and D, Fig. 1(a)) while off Ortigueira Ria surface temperature values were
214 lower (14°C) (st. A and B, Fig. 1(a)). These high water temperature values are similar to
215 the ones observed for a summer situation due to solar heating (Alvarez et al., 2003;
216 Alvarez et al., 2005), however, air temperature during the previous days of the cruise under
217 study (November 18) never surpassed 10°C. Therefore, these conditions can only be
218 related to the IPC influence.

219 Several studies (Frouin et al., 1990; Haynes and Barton, 1990) have found that around
220 the western Galician margin, IPC can be identified by means of thermohaline
221 measurements as a high salinity water body located along the shelf break. The highest
222 salinity values (~35.9) can be measured around 100m deep decreasing upward where the
223 maximum temperature values (~16.5°C) can be found. Recently, Huskin et al. (2003) and
224 Torres and Barton (2006) characterized a poleward intrusion in October-November 1999 at
225 the shelf break off Galician coast (between 8.5-9.5°W). IPC salinity and temperature values
226 at surface layers were very similar to the ones observed in November 2008 at the northern
227 Galician shelf.

228 The hydrographical and biogeochemical patterns were also analyzed along the main
229 channel of the northern Rias (st. 3 to st. 7, Fig. 1(a)) to better characterize the influence of
230 the IPC. Only the Barqueiro Ria is shown (Fig. 4). The highest salinity (35.6) and
231 temperature (15°C) values were observed close to the mouth of the ria (st. 7, Fig. 4)
232 decreasing innerward and showing that IPC is only present at the external part. The same
233 pattern was also observed at Viveiro Ria (not shown). This situation can be explained due
234 to the influence of river discharge at the inner part of the rias, which contributes to prevent
235 the IPC penetration inside them. In fact, river discharge at O Barqueiro Ria measured the
236 day before the cruise (Table I) was two times higher than the annual average flow of about
237 $6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. A similar situation was previously described at the western Galician rias where the

238 river runoff originates a low salinity water plume which contributes to the formation of the
239 Western Iberia Buoyant Plume (WIBP, Peliz et al., 2002). This buoyancy plume extends
240 along the coast and under upwelling favourable conditions is advected offshore and can
241 block the entrance of seawater throughout surface layers. Although the cruise at the
242 northern Galician rias (November 18) was carried out after four consecutive days of
243 upwelling favorable conditions, the effect of the river plume was only observed inside the
244 rias (Fig. 4). It is necessary to take into account that the freshwater input at the western
245 Galician rias (total annual average flow $\sim 134 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) is higher than at the northern ones
246 (total annual average flow $\sim 17 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$).

247 IPC also affect the biogeochemical properties. Southward of Cape Estaca de Bares,
248 inside Barqueiro and Viveiro Rias, a river-ocean gradient of nutrient salts resulting from
249 fluvial contributions (Table I) was observed and exemplified by the Barqueiro Ria (Fig. 4).
250 A little biological activity was found near surface (Varela et al., 2005), as shown in the
251 chlorophyll concentrations. At the ria mouth bottom, close to the thermohaline gradient
252 resulting from IPC influence, there was a small dissolved oxygen depletion (90% of
253 oxygen saturation) and a light increase of nitrate and phosphate concentrations while the
254 ammonium maximum was observed at 15-20m deep. This situation corresponds to the
255 typical “en echelon” distribution of organic matter remineralization in rias (Prego et al.,
256 1999). Offshore the ria, near Cape Estaca de Bares, nutrient salts decreased (Fig. 4). The
257 water mass was poor in nitrate ($< 2 \mu\text{M}$), phosphate ($< 0.1 \mu\text{M}$) and silicate ($< 2 \mu\text{M}$) as it
258 was already observed by Prego et al. (2007) during an IPC intrusion in the western
259 Galician shelf. In the Northern Rias of Barqueiro and Viveiro biogeochemical patterns
260 were disturbed by IPC influence while westward of Cape Estaca de Bares (Ortigueira Ria)
261 this situation was not observed.

262

263 **4. Conclusions**

264

265 The intrusion of a warm water mass related to the IPC was characterized at the
266 northern Galician shelf in November 2008. Sea Surface Temperature images showed that
267 under upwelling favorable conditions the IPC presence was discontinuous along the
268 Galician coast showing a temperature gap between Cape Vilano and Cape Ortegal and a
269 weakening of the temperature signal along the northern coast. In addition, IPC was
270 observed close to the mouth of the northern Galician rias of Barqueiro and Viveiro, around
271 Cape Estaca de Bares, making the water poor in nutrients. The river discharge contributed

272 to prevent the IPC entrance and the effect of the river plume was only observed inside the
273 rias showing a slight biological activity and an estuarine stratification near surface. Taking
274 into account these patterns described above, it is possible to see that particular coastal
275 features as capes and rias play an important oceanographic role in relation to the occasional
276 poleward intrusions near this coast. Consequently, more research would be necessary in
277 order to establish the processes which affect the northern Galician coast in terms of water
278 masses intrusion.

279

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373 eastern boundary of the north Atlantic. *Journal of Marine Research* 34, 131 - 141.
374

375 **Figure Captions**

376

377 **Figure 1.** (a) Map of northern Galician Rias showing the sampling hydrographic stations
378 (black circles and gray polygons). Letters refer to the selected stations to analyze the TS
379 diagram of the water column (Fig. 3). (b) Black dots represent the 5 control points
380 considered to analyze wind data provided by the QuikSCAT. Numbers represent the 5
381 control points located in front of the Northern Galician Rias to analyze the SST data.

382

383 **Figure 2.** (a-f) SST images (color maps) and Ekman transport patterns (black arrows)
384 along the Galician coast from November 14-19. SST images correspond to the date shown
385 in each frame. (g) Evolution of SST data in front of the northern Galician coast (black
386 squares, Fig. 1(b)) and meridional component of Ekman transport (Q_y) (dashed line) from
387 November 14-19. Q_y was calculated by averaging data at the 5 control points located along
388 the northern Galician coast (black dots, Fig. 1(b)). Ekman transport was calculated by
389 averaging transport data for the two previous days to the date shown in each frame.

390

391 **Figure 3.** (a) Temperature distribution at the surface layer (1 m depth) measured at all the
392 sampling stations shown in Fig. 1(a) on November 18. (b) TS diagram of the water column
393 corresponding to inshore and offshore areas (Fig. 1(a)). Ria-mouth stations were named:
394 Om, Bm and Vm (referred to Ortigueira, Barqueiro and Viveiro Rias, respectively) and
395 offshore stations: A, B, E and F. Two stations located at the adjacent shelf around Cape
396 Estaca de Bares (st. C and D) were also considered.

397

398 **Figure 4.** Contour maps of temperature, salinity, oxygen, chlorophyll and nutrient salts
399 along the main channel of the Barqueiro Ria corresponding to the cruise carried out in
400 November 18.

401

Table 1. Discharge and chemical concentrations for the rivers running into the Northern Galician Rias on November 17, one day before the sea cruise.

Ria	River	Flow ($\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Diss. O_2 (μM)	O_2 satur. (%)	Nitrate (μM)	Nitrite (μM)	Ammonium (μM)	Phosphate (μM)	Silicate (μM)	Chlorophyll ($\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$)
Ortigueira	Mera	4.05	12.1	323	96	79.7	0.3	3.4	0.11	156	0.4
O Barqueiro	Sor	12.33	12.3	329	98	41.5	0.0	0.2	0.15	91	0.1
Viveiro	Landro	7.68	12.0	320	95	76.4	0.1	0.8	0.14	142	0.4

Figure 3

Figure 2

Figure 3

November - (O Barqueiro Ria)

Figure 4